

REALISING FOOD DEMOCRACY BY TACKLING “FEAR OF THE MASSES” IN PUBLIC DEBATES

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Summary: The unsuccessful end of the European Union’s Farm to Fork policy is another example of what seems to be an insurmountable gap between the development of ‘good’ strategies and their implementation. This gap necessitates a search for alternative forms of food system governance. Several voices are now calling for governance based on food democracy, with more power in the hands of the populace. However, this call is often jeopardised by a dominant ochlophobia, the fear of the masses, in the public debate. This article explores the importance of overcoming ochlophobia in food system governance and advocates for addressing wealth power as a crucial step forward.

Keywords: *Farm to Fork Strategy, Food Democracy, Ochlophobia, Wealth Power, Food Policy*

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Europe’s unhealthy and unjust food systems. New policies to promote better food environment.

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The gap between policy strategies and policy implementation

At the beginning of 2020, the European Commission launched Farm to Fork (F2F) ¹ a strategy at the heart of the European Union (EU) Green Deal, ² which aimed to make European food systems more just, healthy, and environmentally friendly. The approach of F2F was quite ‘new’, as it moved beyond a narrow focus only on food production to consider all parts of the food value chain, including production, processing, distribution, retail, consumption, and waste management.

As outlined online* and defined by the Food and Agricultural Organisation

* See Global Food System Map at: <https://image.slidesharecdn.com/shiftnlobalfoodsystemmaps-160114131223/75/Global-Food-System-Map-2-2048.jpg>

(FAO), food systems “encompass the entire range of actors and their interlinked value-adding activities involved in the production, aggregation, processing, distribution, consumption and disposal of food products that originate from agriculture, forestry or fisheries, and parts of the broader economic, societal and natural environments in which they are embedded.” ³ This comprehensive perspective was finally placed at the forefront of the EU food policy agenda with F2F.

The political debate surrounding F2F in the following years was intense, especially with respect to the implementation of the legislative framework for sustainable food systems (FSFS), ⁴ the flagship initiative of F2F. FSFS was supposed to be implemented by the European

Commission by the end of 2023, but eventually, almost all the policies foreseen by F2F have been paused or dismissed.⁵ What started as a strategy promising to finally implement a systemic view for EU food system governance eventually became another example of a good strategy that was watered down before its implementation.

The reasons for this failure are multiple and complex but a key factor was the significant power inequality among the different food value chain stakeholders in their ability to influence EU food system policymaking. In particular, and in line with what was highlighted by recent literature on the Commercial Determinants of Health (CDoH)⁶ (World Health Organization, 2024), a key issue was the disproportionate influence corporate lobbies have on the policy process, and especially on food system governance.

The strategies used by the agri-food corporations are similar to those used by tobacco, alcohol and fossil fuel corporations. Lobbying is the most documented activity,⁷ but there are several other ways large food corporations influence governance. These include influencing the political economy framework to favour neoliberal economic policies,⁸ limiting corporate liability,⁹ and creating doubts about the value and legitimacy of opposition from academics and civil society organisations.¹⁰

Currently, it is difficult to pinpoint causal linkages between these different activities and their influence on policymaking and governance, but some instances of the impact of corporate lobbying are well documented. For example, the implementation of the mandatory Front of Package Labelling¹¹ and the legislation on the reduction of chemical pesticides were heavily influenced by corporate lobbying (see article by Kokole et al., in this issue).

Given the importance of the EU's food systems, a fundamental question is not *if* but *how* we can prevent this type of interference from occurring again in the future.

Table 1: Approaches to food system governance that empower the populace

APPROACH	KEY FEATURES
Food Sovereignty	This is the right of individuals, peoples, communities, and countries to define their own food policies which are ecologically, socially, economically and culturally appropriate to their unique circumstances. This paradigm focuses on developing forms of collective autonomy across the food value chain, from production to waste, at a local level, so that control over the food system remains in the hands of farmers, for whom farming is both a way of life and a means of producing food.
Food citizenship	Centres on the competencies and skills that individuals need so they can act as food citizens, namely actors that are not involved only as consumers in the food system, but as participants who shape it. Stressing this division between consumers and citizens helps to explain that individuals must be better aware of how the food system works, more involved in the decision-making process, better educated about the processes structuring current decisions. Moving from consumers to citizens, individuals can thus increase their willingness to create a just and sustainable food system.
Food as commons	Aims to deconstruct food as a commodity and treat it instead as, what Ostrom called, a 'commons' – namely a resource that is rivalrous and non-excludable. In other words, the use of the resource by one person reduces availability to others and it is difficult to prevent access to the resource by others. A key aspect of this paradigm is that problems of the food system are based on the commodification of food, which is structural to prioritising economic profit over other values. To change this, it is necessary that food system governance is based on food as a commons, which will allow more just and equal forms of management of the commons.
Food Democracy	This is the paradigm that focuses most on food governance, since it focuses on the structures and social processes that are necessary to make sure that people – and not just a few technocrats – are more involved in the control of the food system. In this way then, it can be conceived as the discussion on which institutions, processes and structures are needed to realise food citizenship and food sovereignty.

Source: authors' own

The problem of ochlophobia in current forms of governance

Over the last few decades, there have been several attempts to develop alternative approaches to the neoliberal paradigm that has dominated recent food system governance (see Table 1). These approaches include paradigms such as Food Sovereignty,¹² Food Citizenship,¹³ Food Democracy¹⁴ and Food as Commons.¹⁵

Though differing in their approaches, a commonality across these paradigms is the need to move beyond commoditised food systems managed primarily for the profit of large corporations, towards empowering the populace in decision-making.

However, following the dominant rhetoric of the political debate in recent years, one might question whether this is really the solution we should pursue. Given the occurrence of events like the election of Donald Trump in the United States,

Brexit in the United Kingdom, the rise of demagogic governments in several European Member States, and the shift of several political parties towards more right-wing positions, are we sure that giving more power to the people is the solution to fix the current problems of the EU's food system governance?

The authors believe the answer to this question is 'yes'. Furthermore, we believe that a core element that will help to underscore the importance of giving more power to the people lies within a concept that may be unfamiliar to many but is essential for understanding current political events: *ochlophobia*.

In standard dictionaries, ochlophobia is defined as the 'extreme or irrational fear or dislike of the crowds'. In politics, this term reflects the fear that masses (due to their perceived irrationality, and uncontrollable behaviour) may jeopardise the stability and overall functioning of a state. The

dominant political rhetoric that followed the aforementioned events is based on this fear. However, this rhetoric is wrong.

First of all, while it is not possible to present here all the evidence to deconstruct the biases exposed by recent political literature, citizens are not as ignorant, irrational and racist as the political debate is depicting them.¹⁶ To take just one example, many seem to have forgotten that in 1975 the United Kingdom already had a popular referendum to determine whether to remain in the European Community. The ‘remain side’ won by a large margin, despite the fact that racism and anti-immigrant rhetoric were endemic issues of the 60s and 70s United Kingdom politics. Hence, it would be wrong to maintain that Brexit occurred because United Kingdom citizens are now much more racist and ignorant than before.¹⁷

Furthermore, aforementioned events did not occur as a result of a popular revolt by the masses. On the contrary, these events followed standard democratic procedures, where demagogic parties are able to exploit fallacies in the system¹⁸ and to convey popular discontent into a successful political agenda. This distinction is crucial because the difference between “political engineering” and “mass revolt” goes beyond semantics; it reflects different targets in addressing what we perceive as issues within a democratic system. The former entails that demagogues are exploiting a rigged system for their own interests, while the latter entails a spontaneous action by crowds who, driven by intrinsic biases, end up threatening the well-functioning of society.

As already pointed out centuries ago by Machiavelli in the *Discourses*, the story of democracy and other republics has always been connected to the question of who is the best “guardian of liberty”: the many (the population) or the few (the wealthy elites)? It follows that the main political concern becomes who must control the other side.¹⁹

The ochlophobic view is concerned with the tyranny of the many, and thus relies on technocratic governments to control this threat. Democratic republicanism, the

opposite view, has wealth power as the biggest threat posed to common liberty. By relying on the latter, the goal becomes to control wealth power to prevent it from using common institutions to favour their own interests at the expense of societal wellbeing. It is important to stress here that politicians are theoretically external to this duality and are the “object” the two sides compete for. Therefore, the problem is not that policymakers are always on the side of the ‘few’, but that if the ‘many’ do not democratically control, or have the opportunity to control, wealth power, then wealth power will be used by the few to sway governments to work for their wealth accumulation rather than the people’s and society’s wellbeing.

This change in perspective is essential to address the problems of the current European food system. The impact of CDoH has resulted in situations where ‘food billionaires’ have increased their wealth by \$382 billion over the last two years, leading to 62 new food billionaires since the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic.²⁰ Based on this alone, there are strong grounds to maintain that food system governance should be based on democratic republicanism for which concentrated wealth, and not the tyranny of the majority, is the main concern to be tamed.

The solution: A food democratic republicanism

A shift of power towards the many is the basic concept of food democracy. A summary of the literature identified four general types of power in our societies, which are also important for governance:²¹

- Power over (ability to influence or coerce)
- Power to (organise and change existing hierarchies)
- Power with (power from collective action)
- Power within (power from individual consciousness)

All four of these must be tackled if we are to realise a food democratic republicanism.

A practical example of a fairer distribution of ‘power over’ and ‘power to’ is the creation of food citizens’ panels²² at EU level, which several voices would now like to see as a permanent practice.²³ While these bodies have proven to be effective for specific issues (e.g., food waste in the case of the European Commission panels), unless they specifically target the influence of wealth power over food system governance, they are unlikely to lead to a more just, healthy, and sustainable European food system. For this change to happen, popular participation must be intertwined with systemic regulations targeting CDoH. Examples of systemic regulations that could create more balanced ‘power over’ and ‘power to’ are described in **Table 2**.

These are just some of the actions required to improve European food system governance. Food systems are a complex network involving actors, relationships, and legislation across multiple sectors. Mentioning the need to change food systems is akin to saying that we must change our societies; and in a way, there is truth in this.

In addition to creating a better balance of the distribution of the ‘power over’ and ‘power to’, more opportunities for the manifestation of the ‘power with’ and ‘power within’ are essential so that decisions about food systems are devolved, shaped and taken at more local levels. There are promising examples of this happening with cooperative movements in food systems, such as Morgenrot in Austria (which engages with all key stakeholders in the regional food system [producers, direct marketers, food processors, transporters, stores, online stores] to ensure that producers are producing food sustainably, consumers have access to healthier and more sustainable regional and seasonal products and that both are tied through fair pricing) but more needs to be done to realise a true food democratic republicanism.

Conclusion

The narrow concentration of wealth power has negatively affected our societies for centuries. Food systems are just one area where the commodification of a

commons has led to dynamics focused on maximising corporate profit at the expense of the people's health and Europe's sustainability. A food democracy republicanism can be achieved only if power inequalities are addressed at all levels of society, manifested as the power over, power to, power with and power within. Recent developments in the Economy of Wellbeing²⁴ point in this direction and they highlight that we can only achieve an equitable, just and well functioning economic system if we set people's wellbeing as a societal goal. A more just, healthier and more sustainable food system is a central piece in this bigger puzzle.

This article proposes two initial steps towards achieving these goals. First, food democracy institutions must genuinely engage citizens in the governance of the system, granting them decision-making power over outcomes rather than involving them merely to gather opinions in consultation processes.

Second, wealth power must be recognised as a major threat and policies should specifically target CDoH to ensure that there is a more balanced distribution of the 'power over' and 'power to'. History demonstrates that societies function better when wealth power is effectively regulated. EU policies have missed this target for too long, and as a result, there is now overwhelming evidence that European food systems are unjust, unhealthy and unsustainable.

If we aim for European food systems to prioritise health as an absolute value rather than a negotiable one deprioritised for economic profit, it is necessary to control the influence wealth power has over food system governance. Only in this way will it be possible to bridge the gap between strategy and implementation.

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Table 2: Creating more balanced power in food systems

FOOD SYSTEM POLICY GOAL	EXAMPLES
Fairness & transparency	<p>Across the food value chain:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implement transparency disclosure requirements and stricter conflict of interest standards Develop norms to regulate Corporate Social Responsibility practices and their interference in Public Health policies Protect scientific publications from corporate influence, focusing especially on clear funding and Conflict of Interest disclosures
Level playing field	<p>Across the food value chain:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Especially at EU level, address the inequality in access to institutions between industries and civil society organisations²⁴ Prevent "revolving doors" between big corporations and important governmental positions Focus on mandatory regulations versus self-regulatory approaches favoured by the industry
Preventing wealth capture	<p>Across the food value chain:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regulate tax havens, tax evasion, profit repatriation and implement progressive corporate taxation
Protecting population health	<p>Producers and Retailers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implement taxes on foods high in sugar, salt and fat (HFSS) Regulate predatory marketing, especially targeted to children, on all media and especially in digital platforms

Source: authors' own

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